

ON THE FORMATION OF COMPOUNDS IN ORGANIC SOLVENTS.
PART II. FORMATION OF ALKALI AND ALKALINE
EARTH METAL IODOMERCURIATES, ALKALI
METAL IODOCADMIATES AND CADMIUM
IODOMERCURIATES

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The formation of complex and double salts of HgI_2 and CdI_2 with univalent and bivalent metal iodides and also the interaction of HgI_2 and CdI_2 in organic solvents have been studied. The following compounds have been prepared and their properties studied: $NH_4I.HgI_2.C_2H_5OH$; $2NH_4I.CdI_2$; $NH_4I.CdI_2.C_2H_5OH$; $2LiI.HgI_2.6C_2H_5OH$; $NaI.HgI_2.2C_2H_5OH$; $NaI.HgI_2.2HOAc$; $NaI.HgI_2.2(CH_3)_2CO$; $KI.HgI_2.2C_2H_5OH$; $KI.HgI_2.2Py$; $MgI_2.HgI_2.8C_2H_5OH$; $2HgI_2.CaI_2$; $CaI_2.3HgI_2.6C_2H_5OH$; $2I_2.SrI_2$; $CdI_2.3HgI_2$; $HgI_2.2CdI_2$. 10 acetamide; $CdI_2.6$ benzamide; $CdI_2.6Py$ and $HgI_2.2Py$.

The formation of complex and double salts of HgI_2 and CdI_2 with uni- and bivalent metal iodides and also the interaction of HgI_2 and CdI_2 in aqueous medium have been studied by several workers (cf. Mellor, "A Comprehensive Treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry", 1923, Vol. IV, pp. 582-84, 925-47). Hietnan and Siller (*Svensk. Kem. Tied.*, 1947, 59, 228) studied the ternary system, $HgI_2-CdI_2-H_2O$ at 50°, 75°, 100°, and found that tetragonal form of HgI_2 formed mixed crystals containing 0-50% CdI_2 . Practically no work on the subject has been done in non-aqueous media, and the present investigation has therefore been undertaken with a view to studying the formation of double compounds of these iodides in organic solvents.

EXPERIMENTAL

The compounds were all of Merck's E.P. quality and the solvents were dehydrated and distilled. Two sets of experiments under similar conditions in each case were carried out. The results reported are an average of the two values. A measured volume of the solvent was taken in each of the flasks, the components were added alternately till the solution was saturated with respect to both at room temperature (about 25°) and left overnight. It was filtered and the filtrate kept in a vacuum desiccator over $CaCl_2$ in the case of alcohol and over CaO , when acetone was used as the solvent. It took a long time for crystallisation. As the products decomposed slightly on recrystallisation, these were washed once with a minimum quantity of the solvent, filterpressed, dried in a desiccator and examined.

Standard methods of separation and estimation were used. Mercury was estimated as HgS , cadmium as pyrophosphate, strontium as sulphate, iodine as AgI and nitrogen by Kjeldahl's method. Calcium was precipitated as oxalate and determined volumetrically by dissolving it in dilute H_2SO_4 and titrating it against standard $KMnO_4$ solution. In compounds containing mercury and iodine together, the following

procedure for the estimation of iodine was adopted (Caul and Schoonover, *J. Res. Nat. Bur.*, 1941, 26, 481). A known quantity of the substance was heated with 15-20% NaOH solution on a water-bath at about 50°, 1 or 2 c.c. of formaldehyde added to it and heating continued for about half an hour when HgI_2 was reduced completely to metallic mercury. The contents were filtered and washed several times with water. The filtrate and washings were mixed and iodine was estimated as AgI . Nitrogen in the amide compound was estimated by Kjeldahl's method and the nitrogen in pyridine compounds, by heating the substance with about 40% NaOH solution, absorbing the distilled pyridine into a known volume of standard H_2SO_4 , and back-titrating the excess acid with a standard NaOH solution, using methyl orange as indicator (cf. Allen, "Commercial Organic Analysis", 1911, Vol. III, pp. 318-19).

The method of preparation and the properties of the compounds being closely similar, the results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Compound formed.	Characteristic properties.	Found.	Calc.
Alcoholo ammonium tri-iodo-mercuriate $NH_4I.HgI_2.C_2H_5OH$	Deep yellow needles; hygroscopic; decomposing when treated with a large quantity of water or the solvent.	N: 2.13% Hg: 30.98 I: 59.12	2.17% 31.00 59.00
Hexa-alcoholo lithium tetra-iodo-mercuriate $2LiI.HgI_2.6C_2H_5OH$	Do	Hg: 19.94 I: 59.94	20.09 59.86
Di-alcoholo sodium tri-iodo-mercuriate $NaI.HgI_2.2C_2H_5OH$	Yellow plates; other properties as above.	Hg: 28.78 I: 54.69	28.81 54.68
Diacetono sodium tri-iodomercuriate $NaI.HgI_2.2CH_3COCH_3$	Do; very hygroscopic.	Hg: 27.77 I: 52.70	27.84 52.86
Diacetic acido sodium tri-iodo-mercuriate $NaI.HgI_2.2HOAc$	Do	Hg: 27.58 I: 52.63	27.69 52.56
Dialcoholo potassium tri-iodo-mercuriate $KI.HgI_2.2C_2H_5OH$	Do; less hygroscopic than the Na salt.	Hg: 27.96 I: 53.54	28.15 53.44
Dipyridino potassium tri-iodo-mercuriate $KI.HgI_2.2Py$	White crystalline compound; loses pyridine on exposure to the atmosphere and assumes a yellowish tinge.	Hg: 25.65 N: 3.48 I: 48.85	25.77 3.59 48.90
Ammonium tetra-iodo cadmate $2NH_4I.CdI_2$	White, slightly hygroscopic, crystalline mass, decomposing in water.	N: 4.23 Cd: 17.09 I: 77.39	4.27 17.12 77.37
Alcoholo ammonium tri-iodocadmiate (crystallised from the mother-liquor at 0°) $NH_4I.CdI_2.C_2H_5OH$	Do	N: 2.49 Cd: 20.11 I: 68.18	2.51 20.17 68.15
Potassium tetra-iodocadmiate $2KI.CdI_2$	Do; non-hygroscopic.	Cd: 16.04 I: 72.75	16.09 72.68

TABLE I (contd.)

Compound formed	Characteristic properties.	Found.	Calc.
Octo-alcoholo magnesium tetra-iodo-mercurate (from a soln. of the composition $MgI_2 + 1.878HgI_2 + 16$ alcohol and sp. gr. 1.22 at 25°) $MgI_2 \cdot HgI_2 \cdot 8C_2H_5OH$	Yellow; very hygroscopic; prismatic crystals: similar in nature to the alkali metal compounds.	Hg: 18.09 I: 46.26	19.23 46.13
Calcium hexa-iodo-mercuriate $CaI_2 \cdot 2HgI_2$	Do	Hg: 33.22 I: 63.32 Ca: 3.28	33.32 63.32 3.30
Hexa-alcoholo calcium octo-iodo-mercuriate (from the mother-liquor when it was saturated with HgI_2 and cooled at 0°) $CaI_2 \cdot 3HgI_2 \cdot 6C_2H_5OH$	Do	Hg: 31.22 I: 52.65	31.13 52.50
Strontium hexa-iodomercuriate $SrI_2 \cdot 2HgI_2$	Do	Hg: 32.05 I: 60.72 Sr: 6.77	32.13 60.60 7.00
Cadmium octo-iodomercuriate $CdI_2 \cdot 3HgI_2$	Yellow, non-hygroscopic, crystalline compound; other properties as above.	Hg: 34.62 Cd: 6.41 I: 58.68	34.78 6.49 58.70
Deca-acetamido cadmium hexa-iodomercuriate $2CdI_2 \cdot HgI_2 \cdot 10CH_3CONH$	Yellow, non-hygroscopic crystals, m.p. 85-85.5°; soluble in water, alcohol and acetone.	N: 7.75 Hg: 11.20 Cd: 12.82 I: 42.92	7.87 11.28 12.64 42.80
* Hexapyridino cadmium iodide, $CdI_2 \cdot 6Py$	White crystalline compound, m.p. 108-109°; dissolves in hot water.	N: 9.91 Cd: 13.31 I: 30.26	9.99 13.37 30.22
Dipyridino mercuric iodide, $HgI_2 \cdot 2Py$	White crystalline mass, m.p. 110°-12°; loses pyridine on exposure to the atmosphere.	N: 4.52 Hg: 32.66 I: 41.40	4.57 32.75 41.47

* The last but one compound was obtained when a mixture of HgI_2 and CdI_2 was dissolved in warm pyridine and allowed to cool at the room temperature (25°) or to an alcoholic solution of these iodides pyridine was added at the room temperature.

On crystallising the mother-liquor at 0° for 24 hours, the last compound separated out.

The last two compounds in Table I were obtained when HgI_2 or CdI_2 , alone, was treated with pyridine. It appears that after being fully saturated with the maximum number of pyridine molecules, no binding forces are available to form the double compound.

In the case of benzamide, when the mixture of the two iodides was dissolved in the molten solvent, it formed a yellow clear solution, but on solidifying, a waxy mass containing free HgI_2 was obtained. When a mixture of these iodides and benzamide was dissolved in alcohol and kept at 0° for some time, a yellowish crystalline mass, which turned white on washing with alcohol and approximating roughly to $CdI_2 \cdot 6$ benzamide (Found: Cd, 10.66; N, 7.65. Calc. for $CdI_2 \cdot 5.7 C_6H_5CONH_2$: Cd, 10.7; N, 7.6%), m.p. 108°-10° (not sharp), was formed. The mother-liquor, when concentrated, yielded pure HgI_2 and no double compound.

There could be obtained no double compound with Li or Na iodide and CdI_2 in any condition.

From the above experiments it appears that the solubility of CdI_2 or HgI_2 in organic solvents is increased to a considerable extent in presence of alkali or alkaline earth metal iodides; HgI_2 dissolves to a far greater extent in presence of CdI_2 in these media. The compounds formed are similar to those obtained in aqueous medium and generally crystallise with a few molecules of the solvent.

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